

Human Resource Development as envisaged by NEP-2020

Dr. Namdev Shamrao Jadhav

Professor and Head Department of English Shri Shahaji Chhatrapati Mahavidyalaya, Kolhapur

Corresponding Author – Dr. Namdev Shamrao Jadhav

DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.18479830

Abstract:

The present research paper entitled “Human Resource Development as envisaged by NEP-2020” aims to evaluate the measures suggested by National Education Policy-2020 to ensure all-round development of students through holistic education system in India. It also aims to study the issues and challenges in achieving the objectives set for the NEP-2020. It intends to arrive at the conclusion with the emphasis on the right approaches and suggestions in the implementation of this policy in toto in the country.

Keywords: Human Resource Development, Skills, Abilities

Introduction:

Education is the most effective tool for achieving social justice, equality, and civilized society. It is instrumental in achieving full human resource development. The purpose of the education system is to develop good human beings capable of rational thought and action, possessing compassion and empathy, courage and resilience, scientific temper, and creative imagination, with sound ethical moorings and values. Education has always been accorded an honoured place in Indian society. Early education in India commenced under the supervision of a guru and it was delivered through Gurukula. Nowadays formal education is imparted through schools, colleges, and universities. India is the seventh-largest country in the world by area. It is the second largest populated country after China. In the foregoing part of this research paper National Education Policy-2020 will be evaluated and analyzed in its role of human resource development in the country.

Overview of National Education Policy-2020:

National Education Policy-2020 (NEP-2020) is brought into practice with aims and objectives to ensure sustainable growth and

development of India in all sectors. Therefore, it is suggested that the aim must be for India to have an excellent education system that will cater to the diverse needs of Indian population. NEP-2020 proposes the revision and revamping of all aspects of education structure. This policy aims at holistic development of students in the fields such as cognitive, social, ethical, emotional, and professional. NEP-2020 envisions an education system rooted in Indian ethos that contributes directly to transforming India into an equitable and vibrant knowledge society.

NEP-2020 replaces the 10+2 structure implemented by the second National Education Policy (1986) with 5+3+3+4 structure based on the age groups with developmental needs and interests of learners at different stages of early life. The first five years of child education is called Early Childhood Care and Education (ECCE). Ideally it consists of flexible, multi-faceted, multi-level, play-based activity, and inquiry-based learning. The Preparatory Stage will comprise next three years of education with interactive classroom learning. The Middle Stage will comprise further three years of education with the introduction of subject teachers for learning across the sciences, mathematics, arts,

social sciences, and humanities. The Secondary Stage will comprise last four years of school education with focus on multidisciplinary studies. The second part of NEP-2020 covers higher education which plays an extremely important role in promoting human as well as societal well-being and in developing India as envisaged in its Constitution. A quality higher education must enable personal accomplishment and enlightenment, constructive public engagement, and productive contribution to society. The third part of NEP-2020 deals with other key areas such as professional education, adult and life long learning, online and digital education. The last part deals with the implementation process of NEP-2020 in the country.

Challenges in Implementation of NEP-2020:

It is foreseen that there will be some challenges in the implementation of this policy in the country. It is true to some extent that the country is currently in a learning crisis. It is seen that many students fail to attain foundational literacy and numeracy abilities. It can be observed that the higher education system in India is facing some of the major problems such as a severely fragmented higher educational ecosystem, less emphasis on the development of cognitive skills and learning outcomes, a rigid separation of disciplines having early specialization and streaming of students into narrow areas of study, limited access particularly in socio-economically disadvantaged areas, limited teacher and institutional autonomy, inadequate mechanism for merit-based career management and progression of faculty and institutional leaders, lesser emphasis on research and lack of competitive peer-reviewed research funding across disciplines, an ineffective regulatory system, large affiliating universities resulting in low standards of undergraduate education etc.

Initiatives Proposed by NEP-2020 for Human Resource Development:

The most important initiative proposed by NEP-2020 is to provide effective and sufficient infrastructure. It also proposes to achieve universal participation in school by carefully tracking students. It recommends that learning environments are engaging and supportive and it should help the students to attain success. NEP-2020 proposes education of diverse disciplines. The introduction of varied courses, with the aims of developing skills and abilities, will acquaint the students with innovative practices and methodologies. The varied verticals of education will enable the students with job ready skills in many sectors. NEP-2020 recommends the courses to be aligned with the essential skill development. These courses will equip the students with the skills of the 21st century. The broad skills include critical thinking, creativity, communication, collaboration, digital literacy, information literacy and life skills like adaptability, leadership and initiative, media literacy, flexibility, productivity, and social skills.

NEP-2020 envisions a complete overhaul and re-energizing of the higher education system to overcome the challenges. It has suggested that State/Union Territories will address the challenges by adopting innovative mechanisms to group or rationalize schools. It proposes multidisciplinary universities and HEI clusters/ Knowledge hubs to make educational system more vibrant. It promotes autonomy so that the HEIs can take quick decisions and ensure development at fast pace.

NEP-2020 proposes holistic and multidisciplinary education which aims to develop all capacities of the students— intellectual, aesthetic, social, physical, emotional, and moral in an integrated manner. This can be seen as the need of the hour. NEP-2020 recommends vocational education to increase employability as well as to promote self-

employment. National Skill Qualification Framework (NSQF) will design discipline specific courses to promote vocational education in the country. NEP-2020 has recommended National Research Foundation to promote quality research in all fields in the country. It proposes that the best teachers enter in this profession. It recommends a pupil-teacher ratio (PTR) of under 30:1 at the level of school to impart quality education. It also recommends that the appointments of teachers on the regular basis be made at the earliest. It suggests that the harmful practice of excessive teacher transfers should be stopped in order to provide consistent role models to the learners. It suggests that teachers will be given continuous opportunities for self-development and to learn the latest innovations and advances in the professions.

NEP-2020 promotes extensive use of technology to reach the needs of diverse types of learners. High quality educational resources will be made available through the platforms like Digital Infrastructure for Knowledge Sharing (DIKSHA), Study Webs of Active-Learning for Young Aspiring Minds (SWAYAM) etc. It recommends that the students should be given increased flexibility and choice of subjects to study so that they can align their education on their abilities and interests. It can be said that NEP-2020 is in complete consonance with the provisions of the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (RPWD) Act 2016 and ensures barrier free education to all children with disabilities.

Finally, NEP-2020 recommends Higher Education Commission of India (HECI) as the highest governing body for education system in India. HECI will look after the four major verticals proposed for the education system in India. The first vertical of HECI will be the National Higher Education Regulatory Council (NHERC). The second vertical will be called

National Accreditation Council (NAC). The third vertical will be the Higher Education Grants Council (HEGC) and the fourth vertical will be the General Education Council (GEC). It also recommends that all professional councils will perform under Professional Standard Setting Bodies (PSSBs). It suggests experiential learning at all stage with the integration into arts, sports, and culture.

Conclusion:

It can be said that education is the most effective tool for developing human resource. It is a great leveler and is the best tool for achieving economic and social mobility, inclusion and equality. It can be stated firmly that India has made remarkable strides in recent years in attaining near-universal enrollment in elementary education. NEP-2020 is implemented with the aim of redefining the education system in India. It is necessary to overcome some of the barriers in the implementation process of NEP-2020 in the country. It will, then, ensure cognitive development of the learners and will be successful in creating holistic and well-rounded individuals equipped with the key 21st century skills. It can be said that NEP-2020 will be successful in developing skilled human resources to work effectively in all sectors of jobs in the years to come.

References:

1. Arora, Pankaj and Haneet Gandhi. eds. *National Education Policy-2020: Paving Ways for Transformational Reforms*, Shipra Publications, 2023.
2. Sharma, Rajesh Kumar. *New Education Policy in India 2020*, S. K. Book Agency, New Delhi. 2022
3. Mankar, Sudhakar. *National Education Policy on Higher Education: 2020*, Atul Publications, Kolhapur. 2022
4. en.wikipedia.org